

Estimating an Optimal Neighborhood Size in the Spherical Self-Organizing Feature Map

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Abstract—This article presents a short discussion on optimum neighborhood size selection in a spherical self-organizing feature map (SOFM). A majority of the literature on the SOFMs have addressed the issue of selecting optimal learning parameters in the case of Cartesian topology SOFMs. However, the use of a Spherical SOFM suggested that the learning aspects of Cartesian topology SOFM are not directly translated. This article presents an approach on how to estimate the neighborhood size of a spherical SOFM based on the data. It adopts the L-curve criterion, previously suggested for choosing the regularization parameter on problems of linear equations where their right-hand-side is contaminated with noise. Simulation results are presented on two artificial 4D data sets of the coupled Hénon-Ikeda map.

Keywords—Parameter estimation, self-organizing feature maps, spherical topology.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE Self-Organizing Feature Maps (SOFMs) [1] is a class of neural networks capable of recognizing the main features of the data they are trained on. There is extensive literature on its biological and mathematical concepts and even more on its implementation in a variety of areas including medicine, finance, chaos and data mining in general ([2]-[6]). It is an unsupervised learning algorithm that clusters data while it is simultaneously attempting to preserve the topology of the input space within the structure of its predefined lattice. Selected examples on the various implementations of the SOFM and the different ways of visualizing the data using SOFMs can be found in [2], [3], and [5].

Adaptive learning is realized by exploiting redundant and complementary information embedded in the data.

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Organization of the input is brought about by lateral interaction among the nodes (cluster units) in the SOFM lattice. Higher the degree of lateral interaction, greater is the degree of organized learning. Lateral interaction among the cluster units in the SOFM lattice is primarily determined by the topology of the lattice. Topology, in this context, is defined as the geometric connectivity between the cluster units or nodes in the grid that represents the configuration of the SOFM space. Therefore, a topological discontinuity in the lattice will restrict the lateral interaction between the cluster units and therefore restrict learning.

The Spherical SOFMs (S-SOFMs), introduced [7] as a natural extension of the SOFMs, have an inherit capability of visualizing high dimensional data ([8]-[11]). This is attributed to the spherical topology of the SOFM lattice which not only has an overall symmetry and continuity in its structure, but also provides a 3D framework for visualizing the data.

Key parameters of learning in the SOFM include the neighborhood size, the learning rate, and convergence of the algorithm. While much has been published on estimating the neighborhood size in Cartesian topology SOFMs, there is no literature on the S-SOFMs regarding this parameter. Extensive implementation of the spherical SOFM suggested that the lessons learned in the case of Cartesian topology SOFMs did not directly translate to S-SOFMs. This article discusses how to estimate an optimal neighborhood size in an S-SOFM. It is inspired by the findings from fundamental research literature on the regularization parameter on system of linear equations. Its implementation is illustrated using examples of simulated chaotic data.

II. THE SPHERICAL SELF ORGANIZED FEATURE MAP

An S-SOFM (also known as “glyph”) is essentially a non-linear mapping from the data space to the surface of a sphere. The data space is usually of Cartesian form, but can also be of any other form. If \mathbf{P} represents the m-dimensional spatially continuous input space that comprises of a set of activation patterns, defined by metric relationship $\mathbf{p}_i \in \mathbf{P}$, and \mathbf{w} denotes the spatially discrete S-SOFM space (Fig. 1), then, in the mathematical sense the S-SOFM non linear transformation may be expressed as

$$\Phi : \mathbf{P} \rightarrow \mathbf{w} \quad (1)$$

where Φ is the S-SOFM non-linear mapping between the m-

dimensional input data space and the m-dimensional weight vectors of the SOFM space. The SOFM space is represented by a network of inter-connected nodes, where each node has a weight vector associated with it which is of the same dimension as the input space. During learning, every input vector gets assigned to a cluster unit whose weight vector is closest to it in the Euclidean sense.

$$w_j(\text{new}) = w_j(\text{old}) + a \cdot h(r,s) \cdot [p_i - w_j(\text{old})] \quad (2)$$

where 'a' is the learning parameter and $h(r,s)$ is the neighborhood function. This function is of the form $h(r,s) = \exp(-r^2/(sR))$, where 's' is the neighborhood size parameter, and 'R' is the size of the neighborhood that is able to cover a hemisphere and it is considered constant. The hemisphere is the largest possible neighborhood that can be considered.

The cluster units in the S-SOFM space therefore represent a reduced set of "internally ordered" prototypical representation vectors of the input space. The fundamental assumption of the S-SOFM algorithm is that clusters existing in the input space will also exist in the low-dimensional mapping space. Therefore the distribution of the input vectors in the S-SOFM space will reflect some physical aspects of the data. Associations between the numeric vectors are reflected in the relative topological positions of the cluster units on the grid, to which they have been assigned.

Fig. 1 The spherical self-organizing feature map [8]

Learning in the S-SOFM takes place due to lateral interaction between neighboring nodes. Therefore the lattice of the S-SOFM plays a significant role in the learning process. A discontinuity in the lattice will result in a restricted neighborhood and consequently restrict learning. In the more common 1- and 2- dimensional SOFM some researchers have investigated different ways to find the optimal learning parameters [12].

III. THE NEIGHBORHOOD PARAMETER BY THE L-CURVE CRITERION

The neighborhood size is essentially a regularization parameter. One of the most promising methods for estimating the regularization parameter is the L-curve criterion [13]. This criterion is widely used in linear algebra problems for handling solutions of linear systems with more equations than unknowns, and has found applications in image de-blurring. The algorithm of this criterion can be summarized in the following steps:

- 1) Estimate the smoothness and the accuracy for a wide range of the regularization parameter.
- 2) Plot smoothness (horizontal axis) against accuracy (vertical axis). The resulting plot should be L-shaped (Fig. 2).
- 3) The corner of the L-shape corresponds to the optimum regularization parameter. It is a value that results both high smoothness and high accuracy.

The original L-curve plot [13], requires accuracy and smoothness to be plotted on the log-log scale. If this rule is relaxed using a linear scale on both axes, as is the case in the example data set presented in this article, the result is a sharp curve.

Fig. 2 The ideal L-curve shape
 Note that in practice the curve may not be so sharp

In the L-curve criterion, smoothness is defined as the sum of distances between each vertex of the glyph (w_j) and the mean of its nearest neighbors (\bar{w}_j). The lesser this sum, smoother is the glyph. Likewise, accuracy is defined as the sum of the distances between each pattern (p_i) and its closest feature (w_j).

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

Consider two data sets formed by the time series of the Hénon map [14] (x and y) and the Ikeda map [15] (u and v) of lengths $N_1=1024$ and $N_2=4096$

$$\begin{aligned}
 x_{i+1} &= 1 - 1.4x_i^2 + y_i \\
 y_{i+1} &= 0.3x_i \\
 u_{i+1} &= 1 + 0.9(u_i \cos(t_i) - v_i \sin(t_i)) \\
 v_{i+1} &= 0.9(u_i \sin(t_i) + v_i \cos(t_i)) \\
 t_i &= 0.4 - \frac{0.6}{1 + u_i^2 + v_i^2}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3}$$

All the time series are standardized in order to have mean 0 and standard deviation 1. The first data set forms a 1024-by-4 pattern space $\mathbf{P}_1 = [\mathbf{x}_1 \ \mathbf{y}_1 \ \mathbf{u}_1 \ \mathbf{v}_1]$ (where \mathbf{x}_1 , \mathbf{y}_1 , \mathbf{u}_1 , and \mathbf{v}_1 are column vectors of length 1024) and the second data set forms a 4096-by-4 pattern space $\mathbf{P}_2 = [\mathbf{x}_2 \ \mathbf{y}_2 \ \mathbf{u}_2 \ \mathbf{v}_2]$ (where \mathbf{x}_2 , \mathbf{y}_2 , \mathbf{u}_2 , and \mathbf{v}_2 are column vectors of length 4096).

These 4 dimensional objects are very complex and cannot be visually perceived. They cannot be projected in a lower dimensional space because they have non-linear dependencies within them, which will be lost due to linear projection. Therefore non-linear data projection techniques to create meaningful low-dimensional representations of the data are much needed.

Fig. 3 Two glyphs of the data set \mathbf{P}_1 . For (a) we set $s=2^1$ (which is very smooth but inaccurate) and for (b) we set $s=2^{-3}$ (which is very rough, and at the same time it is indicative of being over-fitted on the data)

Fig. 4 The L-curve for the data set \mathbf{P}_1 and the corresponding glyph for the optimal value of s , which is $2^{-0.5}$.

Fig. 5 Two glyphs made by the data set \mathbf{P}_2 . For (a) we set $s=2^1$ (which is very smooth but inaccurate) and for (b) we set $s=2^{-3}$. (which is very rough, and at the same time gives the impression of being overfitted on the data)

Fig. 6 The L-curve for the data set P_2 and the corresponding glyph for the optimal value of s , which is $2^{-0.5}$

The main disadvantage in the implementation of the S-SOFM so far is the absence of a criterion to choose an optimal neighborhood size parameter 's'. A large neighborhood results in smoother glyphs (which is desirable), but ignores the small-scale features. On the other hand, a small neighborhood takes into account all the features, no matter how large they are, but results in rough glyphs (which is undesirable). Therefore a cut-off point should be considered as the best tradeoff between smoothness and accuracy. Figs. 3 and 5 show the glyphs of the pattern space for neighborhoods that belong to the 2 extremes (i.e. $s=2^1$, and $s=2^{-3}$), while Figs. 4 and 6 shows the L-curves and the glyphs obtained by the optimum neighborhood parameter choice.

As observed in Figs. 4 and 6, the neighborhood size parameter 's' is neither dependent on the length of the data set, nor on the resolution of the glyph. The optimum parameter size is the same on the short and the long data sets (P_1 and P_2 respectively). Moreover, the glyphs of Figs. 3 and 4 have 642 nodes, while the glyphs of Figs. 5 and 6 have 2562 nodes. We observe that in both cases of glyph resolution the optimum parameter size is the same. This result is very desirable since it indicates that the proposed method defines a neighborhood selection parameter which is dependent on the nature of the data features and not on other parameters irrelevant to them (like the length of the data set or the resolution of the glyph).

V. CONCLUSIONS

A method for choosing the neighborhood size parameter regarding the Spherical Self Organizing Feature Maps was presented. This method provides a means to visualize high dimensional data as both smooth and detailed objects. It is based on the L-curve criterion which has been successfully applied on regularization problems in the past.

Future research in enhancing the potential of the Spherical SOFM as a data visualization tool requires an automatic estimation of the neighborhood parameter. This will save computational time in the proposed trial-and-error approach that examines different values of 's' prior to estimating an optimal value.

Another aspect of interest is the estimation of a reasonable number of training cycles (epochs). In the examples that were discussed, the data were trained for at most 60 cycles. Intuitively, this may be over-spending for the computational time. Unfortunately, inferences in this regard cannot be made based on existing methods for estimating the SOFM parameters. Although the performance of these methods have been successfully demonstrated in 1- and 2- dimensional SOFMs, additional research and testing is required to relatively comment in the context of the spherical SOFM.

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